

The Breaking of Classical Mechanics Through the Lorentz Invariant $A = -Et+px$?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 18, 2024

Special relativity is a theory which is compatible with classical mechanics, yielding the nonrelativistic form of classical mechanics in the $v \ll c$ limit. Alternatively, the definition of velocity, dx/dt , means that one may shift all x points by an arbitrary δ_1 and all t points by an independent arbitrary value δ_2 . For simplicity, we consider a constant v . Given finite shifts, δ_1 and δ_2 , one may Lorentz transform these to δ_1' and δ_2' as well as inverse Lorentz transform them, starting with δ_1' , δ_2' . In this case, the choice of $\delta_2' = \hbar/E$ and $\delta_1' = \hbar/p$, with the assumption of finite variations, leads to $\delta_2 = 0$.

The problem with this classical result is the following, we argue. If one considers the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t + px$ with $p=0$, then if x is finite, one has: $-Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t$. A shift of $t' = \hbar/E$ and $x' = \hbar/p$ leaves the LHS equals 0 meaning a 0 shift to t in the rest frame. This approach is consistent with classical thinking. The problem is that if one tries to associate the shifts with E and p , namely apply the frame independent formulas \hbar/E and \hbar/p , then in the rest frame, the shifts should be $\delta_2 = \hbar/m_0 c^2$ and $\delta_1 = \hbar/p$, but $p \rightarrow 0$. This means that $\delta_1 \rightarrow \infty$ as $1/p$. The issue is that δ_1 does not Lorentz transform.

The notion of a Lorentz transformation is to keep the physics classical which means that introducing shifts \hbar/E for t and \hbar/p for x breaks with the notion of classical physics. One may certainly create shifts and define them any way one wishes it seems, but this may lead to a break with the notion of Lorentz transformations as in the \hbar/p case. Thus, the two sets of ideas seem to be related to two different kinds of physics, the Lorentz transformation being classical physics, and the shifts, quantum mechanics. Given the freedom one has in introducing shifts to x and t , one might suggest experiments which might be able to distinguish an \hbar/p shift in x . This has already been done many years ago in the 2-slit interference case.

The Classical Notion of Shifting x and t by Constants

The definition of velocity in one direction is: dx/dt ((1))

This indicates that one may shift all x points by the same constant δ_1 and all t points by the independent arbitrary constant δ_2 and retain the same velocity. This represents a shift in the origins of t and x . Furthermore, it seems that there is no reason that one could not suggest $t\text{-shift} = \text{Function}_1(E)$ and $x\text{-shift} = \text{function}_2(p)$ in each frame. This, however, may or may not be compatible with Lorentz transformations.

Lorentz Transformations of Shifts in x and t

One may consider the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} |g \quad gv| \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Here } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |gv \quad g| \end{aligned}$$

and apply it to the shifts ($\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2$). This yields:

$$\Delta t_1' = \gamma(\Delta t_1 + v \Delta t_2) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t_2' = \gamma(v \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2) \quad ((3b))$$

Alternatively, one may start with $\Delta t_1'$ and $\Delta t_2'$ in the moving frame and use ((2) with $v \rightarrow -v$ to obtain the inverse transformation. This yields:

$$\Delta t_1 = \gamma(\Delta t_1' - v \Delta t_2') \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t_2 = \gamma(-v \Delta t_1' + \Delta t_2') \quad ((4b))$$

One may then see that by choosing: $\Delta t_1' = 1/v$ and $\Delta t_2' = 1$ that $\Delta t_2 = 0$.

An alternative choice is: $\Delta t_1' = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t_2' = \hbar/E$, also yielding $\Delta t_2 = 0$ ((5)).

One may choose any shift scheme one wishes it seems. An immediate issue with ((5)), however, is that as $p \rightarrow 0$ (it is 0 in the rest frame), $\Delta t_1'$ approaches infinite, but in principle one may use this shift.

One may note, however, that choice of shifts based on E and p , namely \hbar/E and \hbar/p breaks the Lorentz transformation. In particular, we see from ((4)) that \hbar/E and \hbar/p lead to $\Delta t_2 = 0$, when it should be \hbar/mc in the rest frame. Thus, one cannot maintain the Lorentz transformation for shifts and the rule that $\Delta t_1 = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t_2 = \hbar/E$. There is, however, no reason we know of, for rejecting a priori this choice of shifts. It just happens that they break the Lorentz transformation and in doing so, classical mechanics. Here we assume that the Lorentz transformation is completely compatible with classical mechanics, In fact, it defines nonrelativistic classical mechanics in the $v \rightarrow c$ limit.

In other words, if one choose \hbar/E and \hbar/p as shifts for t' and x' in the moving frame, and notes that these are finite in the moving frame, the Lorentz transformation would imply that in the rest frame:

$$\Delta t_2 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t_1 = \gamma/E (1 - vv/cc)/v \quad ((6))$$

If one considers: $-Et' + px' = -mcc t$, and takes delta of this equation, then one has compatibility, but Δt_1 does not equal \hbar/p and Δt_2 does not equal \hbar/E . The idea of a physical result, however, is that it should hold in all frames. Thus, special relativity is incompatible with the idea of an $\hbar/E, \hbar/p$ shift to t and x in all frames. To have this rule, one requires:

$$-Et' + px' = -mcc t + p x \quad \text{such that } p \rightarrow 0 \text{ means that } x \text{ goes as } 1/p \quad ((7))$$

This means that Δt_1 is infinite and Lorentz transforms to an infinite $\Delta t_1'$ whereas one requires \hbar/p .

As a result, we suggest that to retain the rule \hbar/E and \hbar/p for t, x shifts, one must break with the Lorentz transformations, (but only for shifts) and so something more than classical

mechanics seems to be present. One may note that the breaking of the Lorentz transformation of Δt does not mean that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ is broken for this choice of shifts, \hbar/E and \hbar/p . Thus, the shifts are still linked to special relativity, they just do not Lorentz transform.

This, however, must be experimentally verified as it is through the 2-slit experiment, among others.

In other words, the freedom of creating any constant shift of t and x in a frame, and basing these shifts on formulas involving E and p in the frame, which seems consistent with physical rules, breaks with the Lorentz transformation and classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that shifting x and t by a constant does not change velocity $v = dx/dt$. This is a usual origin shift in x, t . One may go further and define these shifts in a given frame any way that one wishes. For example, one may use t shift = \hbar/E and x shift = \hbar/p . It seems that there is no a priori reason that one cannot define shifts based on a physical parameters E and p in each frame. The problem is that these shifts do not Lorentz transform when they should if only classical mechanics is present. In particular, in the rest frame $p=0$ means that $\hbar/p \rightarrow$ infinite. This is still compatible with the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t + px$ because both sides are 0. It is, however, incompatible with the idea of a finite shift Δt which transforms to a finite $\Delta t'$. An infinite shift \hbar/p (for $p=0$) does not Lorentz transform to \hbar/p in the moving frame. Thus, the Lorentz transformation is broken (or does not apply) to this special case of shifts. This suggests that these shifts, if physical, represents a new kind of mechanics, namely quantum mechanics. This does not mean that classical mechanics disappears. It still holds for example for $(0,0)$, $(x=0, t)$ transforming to $(0,0)$, (x', t') such that $v = x'/t'$.